

Structural modification of aluminium alloy for preparation of hydrophobic and antibacterial ZnO-based coatings

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ABSTRACT

By combining mechanical treatment of aluminium alloy with subsequent surface modification using micro-arc oxidation (MAO) technology, zinc oxide (ZnO) oxide coatings were prepared, which achieved enhanced hydrophobic properties, excellent antibacterial activity and corrosion resistance. The coatings were oxidised at different MAO discharge intensities using different frequencies. All surfaces were subjected to determination of wettability, corrosion resistance and chemical stability at 1, 7, 14, and 28 days and antibacterial activity of the coatings against the bacterial population of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* with an evaluation of population inhibition after 24 h. The surfaces mechanically modified by blasting showed a hydrophobic character; their subsequent oxidation by MAO contributed to a significant increase in hydrophobic properties. The sample with the highest Zn content (1.1 wt%), prepared at an MAO source frequency of 222 Hz, i.e. at the most intense plasma discharge, showed the most significant chemical stability in simulated body fluid (SBF) and distilled water and showed the highest antibacterial activity after 24 h. Thus, blasting of aluminium alloy surfaces and their subsequent MAO in alkaline electrolyte allows to obtain oxide coatings with antibacterial, hydrophobic and corrosion-resistant properties with the possibility of their use on surfaces with potential occurrence of harmful bacteria.

1. Introduction

The importance of the spread of bacteria and the number of infections resulting from human contact with pathogenic bacteria is increasing worldwide. Surfaces of materials with a high frequency of contact with the human body represent a reservoir of bacteria and, therefore, an increased risk of bacterial infections. For these reasons, increased disinfection of these surfaces and areas with the need for increased protection against infection becomes increasingly important.

In particular, hospital areas include all medical equipment, instrumentation, handles, handrails, etc. The disadvantage of the application of disinfectants is mainly their short-term effect (about 6 h) and, therefore, the increasing costs associated with the increased use of disinfectants. It is estimated that 20–40 % of infections in healthcare are related to contamination of surfaces with bacteria, viruses, and microorganisms for these reasons [1].

With increasing interest, applications, particularly in the healthcare sector, are increasingly emerging related to functionalising material

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surfaces to achieve an antibacterial effect. This is primarily a solution associated with two basic mechanisms involving resistance to bacterial adhesion or decomposition [2]. Atomic layer deposition (ALD) [3], cold gas spray [4], nitriding [5], chemical vapour deposition (CVD) [6], physical vapour deposition (PVD) [7], electrochemical methods [8] are used to modify the material surfaces of Fe, Ti, Mg, Al alloys for a variety of applications. In addition to surface roughness and wettability, the critical role of modified surfaces is also played by inorganic antibacterial agents incorporated into the surface. The most widely used antibacterial agents in practice include Ag, Cu, and Zn [9]. To ensure a synergistic effect, some studies have used the combination of these substances Cu/Zn [10] and Zn/Ag [11]. In the case of the use of Zn and Cu, these are trace elements present in the human body that support the cardiovascular system and promote osseointegration of implant surfaces [12,13]. Therefore, these elements find application in the surface treatment of medical devices [14,15].

The approach to material surface design is to achieve the required roughness and wetting in various ways in order to achieve the required antibacterial effect for the application. The choice of method and process parameters can effectively influence surface roughness and, therefore, wettability. Over a relatively wide range of roughness, heterogeneously wettable surfaces can be achieved depending on the chosen material type and method; for example, surfaces with superhydrophobic properties ($\theta > 150^\circ$) allow for reduced bacterial adhesion [16], anticorrosive or self-cleaning effect [17]. The roughness of these surfaces can also reduce bacterial adhesion, probably due to the topographical properties of the surface. Surface texture affects bacterial adhesion along with the presence of pores, cracks, pits, or other defects on the functional surface. Also, the size of the substrate-bacteria contact area plays a significant role in cell adhesion, and the presence of air in the substrate structure affects the resulting function of the structured surface [18]. In general, methods that allow surface modification, leading to increased surface roughness and wettability, improve bacterial adhesion [19]. These facts point to the critical role of surface structure in enabling the understanding of bacterial adhesion of structured surfaces.

Recently, the micro-arc oxidation (MAO) method has been increasingly used to modify the surfaces of materials, both in the cast and 3D printed state, mainly due to its cost-effectiveness and environmental impact. The MAO method allows the preparation of ceramic layers on Mg, Al, Ti, Nb, Zr, and Ta alloys to increase wear and corrosion resistance and provide better biocompatibility of the coatings. Other applications of MAO technology include the preparation of coatings with photocatalytic, magnetic, decorative layers and antibacterial properties [20–22]. The effect of antibacterial behaviour of MAO coatings has been studied in most of the works on two important human pathogens, *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), which cause a large number of clinical infections [23]. In the work of Cerchier et al. [24], AA7075 aluminium alloy surfaces were antibacterially modified using the MAO process under alkaline electrolyte conditions. MAO coatings with the presence of silver particles showed an enhanced antibacterial effect of the ceramic coating compared to unmodified and anodised surfaces. To achieve the antibacterial properties of MAO coatings, Cu₂O and ZnO nanoparticles were added to the alkaline electrolyte in the study by Zhao et al. [25]. A different design in the preparation of antibacterial coating on aluminium alloy 5052 was used by Santos et al. [26], where a Cu layer was deposited on the MAO-prepared ceramic layer by cathodic deposition.

This paper focuses on the practical and environmentally friendly preparation of antibacterial coatings for objects exposed to harmful bacteria and thus require special surface treatment. The results present a comprehensive set of findings allowing a detailed description of the critical surface properties in terms of the physical and chemical properties of the layers (e.g. their composition, wettability and roughness) together with the morphology of the base material. Simple procedures involving mechanical and physicochemical methods of layer

preparation were chosen to describe the properties of the layers produced. To achieve antibacterial activity, an oxide surface doped with ZnO was prepared using MAO. The elimination of bacterial activity was evaluated on both the mechanically prepared surface and MAO surfaces prepared at different power efficiencies of the electrochemical source. The results present a simple procedure to modify the surfaces of aluminium alloys to be used for the surfaces of objects exposed to high bacterial activity. Scheme of procedures is shown in Fig. 1.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and modification of the surface

The surfaces of the commonly cast alloy of AlSi1MgMn (20 mm (L)*10 mm (W)*3 mm (H)) were grinded using #400 and #800 grit SiC abrasive papers. The samples were then ultrasonically cleaned in ethanol solution and subsequently air-dried. The samples thus pre-treated were blasted using an injector blast system (GDS Technology s.r.o., Czech Republic) with a working height of 50 mm and a pressure of 2 bar for 5 min. To achieve surface uniformity, synthetic Al₂O₃ with a grain size of up to 0.7 mm was used as the abrasive medium. The mechanically treated samples were then degreased in 1 M NaOH and surface modified with MAO under pilot unit conditions using a pulse source (DEHOR-elspec; Litvinov, s.r.o.). The experiments were performed using pulsed source conditions at a constant voltage of 400 V for 30 min in an alkaline electrolyte of 3 g/L NaOH, 1.0 g/L C₁₀H₁₄N₂Na₂O₈·2H₂O (EDTA), 1.0 g/L C₄H₆O₄Zn·2H₂O (Zinc acetate dihydrate) with conductivity 13.8 mS/cm, pH 12.3. The process conditions of the mechanical surface treatments and the applied MAO technology parameters, including the defined pulse width (t_{on}), time gap (t_{off}) and source frequency, are shown in Table 1.

2.2. Chemical composition and study of morphology

The chemical composition of AlSi1MgMn alloy (Table 2) was determined after decomposition in an acid mixture using atomic emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma (AES-ICP, Spectro Arcross, Germany).

The surfaces of the samples were studied using a JEOL JSM-7610F Plus scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL, Japan). MAO coatings were scanned in backscattered electrons (BSE) (accelerating voltage of 25 keV) with secondary electron detection. The chemical composition of the coating was determined using an energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX, Oxford Instruments). Samples for coating thickness determination by SEM were prepared in sections using mechanical treatment followed by final preparation with PECS II argon ion milling (Gatan, United States) using an accelerating voltage of 8 kV, 90° milling sectors and a processing time of 90 min.

Surface topography was measured using the atomic force microscope (AFM, NenoVision s.r.o.), which was integrated into the SEM system. The system thus designed allows simultaneous SEM and AFM measurements and thus provides a 3D correlative probe and electron microscopy view (CPEM, NenoVision Ltd.). Surface roughness R_a (arithmetic average of the absolute values of the profile heights), R_t (vertical distance between the highest and lowest points of the profile) and R_z (maximum height of the profile), RS_m (arithmetic average width of profile elements), measurements were carried out in contact mode on profilometer device (Talysurf 50, Taylor Hobson).

The chemical state of the samples was evaluated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The spectra were collected by a hemispherical analyser equipped with a multichannel detector using Al K α radiation sources. The spectra were corrected to charging effect. The chemical state of Zn was determined using a modified Auger parameter calculated from the position of the Zn 2p peak at the binding energy scale and the Zn LMM peak at the kinetic energy scale. This parameter is independent of the sample charging. The spectra were interpreted using

Fig. 1. Scheme of procedures for sample preparation and analysis.

Table 1

Process conditions for sample preparation.

Sample	Mechanical treatment	MAO source parameters		
		t_{on} (ms)	t_{off} (ms)	Frequency (Hz)
Sub	grinding	–	–	–
Sp	grinding + blasting	–	–	–
S1	grinding + blasting	0.5	20	49
S2	grinding + blasting	0.5	40	95
S3	grinding + blasting	0.5	4	222

Table 2

Chemical composition AlSi1MgMn alloy.

Sample	Element (wt.%)							
	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mg	Mn	Si	Ti	Zn
AlSi1MgMn	0.17	0.06	0.21	1.40	1.00	0.65	0.09	0.10

the NIST X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy Database [27].

The phase structure of the samples was measured by powder X-ray diffraction (XRPD) using the Rigaku Ultima IV diffractometer (Rigaku Corporation, Japan). X-ray diffraction records were obtained under conditions of Cu K_{α} radiation utilisation at an accelerating voltage of 40 kV, current of 40 mA, Scan speed/Duration time - 1°/min; Step width - 0.02°; Scan range 10–100°. The phase composition was evaluated using the ICDD PDF-2 2022 database.

The contact angle (CA) was measured on an optical tensiometer Theta Flex (Biolin Scientific Sweden). The force Tensiometer Krüss K100 (Krüss GmbH, Germany) was employed to determine the surface tension of the tested liquids. Two liquids were used for the measurements: distilled water (conductivity 3.2 μ S/cm) and simulated body fluid (SBF). SBF was prepared by dissolving NaCl (8.035 g/L), NaHCO₃ (0.355 g/L), KCl (0.225 g/L), K₂HPO₄·3H₂O (0.231 g/L), MgCl₂·6H₂O (0.311 g/L), CaCl₂ (0.292 g/L), Na₂SO₄ (0.072 g/L), Tris (hydroxymethyl)-methylamine (6.118 g/L) and HCl (1 mol/L) to bring the solution to pH 7.4. Measurements were performed using 5 μ L droplets at 7 different locations on the sample. One sample for each liquid was used for measurement. Image processing software ONE Attention was used to evaluate the contact angle.

2.3. Characterisation methods

Antibacterial activity tests were performed according to ISO 22196 (2011)/JIS Z 2801 (2000) and evaluated against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The bacterial strains were cultured on blood agar for 24 h at 37 °C. The test sample surface was rinsed with distilled water, and then the samples were immersed in isopropyl alcohol for 24 h. Bacterial inoculum was prepared for evaluation (measured according to the McFarland scale): *S. aureus* - 1.3 x 10⁵ CFU/ml, *E. coli* - 1.2 x 10⁵ CFU/ml 400 μ l of the tested bacterial inoculum was placed on the test area using pipette and spread over the whole area with an inoculation wand. Cultivation was carried out in a thermostat for 24 h at 37 °C for one series of samples; the second series of samples was carried out without cultivation (time of 0

s). After that time, the bacterial inoculum was rinsed from the entire surface with 10 ml of saline solution in a sterile box. For culture, 1 ml was pipetted and plated onto blood agar – all in triplicates. The blood agar plates were cultured in a thermostat for 24 h at 37 °C. Subsequently, viable bacterial colony-forming units (CFU) were counted, and the assay was evaluated.

The release of Zn from the oxide surface layer was determined by immersion test. Origin substrates, and the samples were immersed in 50 ml of distilled water (pH 4.0) and SBF solutions (pH 7.4) and were shaken in a discontinuous rotation container (10 rpm per minute) at laboratory temperature. 10 ml of solutions were taken from the mixtures at various intervals: 24 h, 7, 14 and 28 days. The total amount of Zn in the origin substrate (Sub) and samples (S1, S2, S3) was determined after the immersion test and their following decomposition in a hot HCl solution (1:1). The concentration of Zn was determined using atomic emission spectrometer with inductively coupled plasma (AES-ICP), Spectro Arcos (SPECTRO Analytical Instruments Inc., Germany). The releasing amount of Zn (R_{Zn} , mg/cm²) from the oxide surface layer was calculated according to Eq. (1):

$$R_{Zn} = \frac{C_{Zn} \cdot V}{1000 \cdot A_{Vz}} \quad (1)$$

Where C_{Zn} (mg/L) – determined concentration of Zn in solution after 24 h, 7, 14 and 28 days respectively.

V (L) – volume of solution during immersion test.

A_{Vz} (cm²) – the total sample surface area.

The releasing part of Zn expressed in % (%Zn) was calculated according to Eq. (2):

$$\text{the \%Zn} = \frac{R_{Zn}}{TC_{Zn}} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

Where: TC_{Zn} (mg/cm²) – total content of Zn on the sample surface, which was calculated as the sum of Zn released during the immersion test and the residual Zn content on the sample after its decomposition in hot HCl.

The corrosion behaviour of the samples was studied in a three-electrode system (Voltalab PGZ 100, France). The samples were connected as working electrodes; a calomel electrode was used as a reflection electrode, and a carbon rod was used as an auxiliary electrode. Potentiodynamic polarisation tests were performed in 3.5 wt% NaCl solution over a sample area of 0.5 cm². The initial potential of the potentiodynamic measurements was set to –150 mV compared to the open circuit potential (OCP) after the corrosion equilibrium was established with a polarisation rate of 5 mV/s. The uncertainty of the polarisation measurements is within 0.5 %.

2.4. Statistical analysis

All experiments and measurements were performed in 3–7 replicates; the results were represented by mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.). The experimental data were subjected to a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's HSD test. Minitab® 17 statistical software was used for the statistical analyses, data visualisation was

performed in OriginPro 8.5 (OriginLab Corporation, USA). Statistical processing of the results of antibacterial tests was carried out using the standard procedure of determining the confidence interval with the extension of the critical values of the Student's distribution, taking into account $n = 3$ and the specificity of these tests. The results were graphed in logarithmic form (base natural logarithm) due to the extensive range of results. In the specific case of continuous coverage of the plate in the antibacterial test (KV – zero antibacterial efficiency, inability to read the number of colonies for extreme counts), only a value without a confidence interval was used for the plots.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of surface topography

Fig. 2 shows the different structurally prepared surfaces of the aluminium alloy. The mechanically prepared surfaces show a different topographic character. The application of grinding and polishing of the aluminium alloy (Fig. 2a) of the Sub sample show traces of tool application. Surface uniformity and removal of grinding marks were achieved by shot blasting (Fig. 2b), where an irregular "sheet" surface texture was formed. Subsequently, MAO technology was used to modify the surface due to the different intensity of the micro-arc discharge. The resulting porous structure typical of MAO (Fig. 2c, d, e) with the presence of pores is influenced by both the previous blast application and the frequency of the spin source used.

Roughness parameters (Fig. 3) were used to assess the surface morphology, they were then statistically evaluated using ANOVA. The results of the most frequently evaluated parameter, R_a , confirmed the rejection of the null hypothesis ($p < 0.01$) that at least one of the means was statistically different. A comparison of samples S1 and S2 after the MAO process and mechanically treated sample Sp shows that they are statistically identical regarding roughness parameter R_a . Consistently, the values of the parameters R_z and R_t for samples S1, S2, and Sp were not found to be statistically significantly different. The surface texture parameters indicate a statistically significant effect of the blasting technology. On the contrary, changes in the surface parameters were identified only when a higher frequency (222 Hz) of the MAO process was applied (Fig. 3), which allowed the preparation of a surface of sample S3 with a statistically significantly different structure compared to the samples Sub, Sp, S1, S2. R_{Sm} parameter was also evaluated, also confirming the statistical agreement between the Sp, S1, and S2 samples.

Sample S3 with MAO coating was also statistically identical to samples Sp and S2 based on the R_{Sm} parameter.

3.2. Thickness and composition of the MAO coatings

The application of different frequencies of the MAO source for 30 min had no significant effect on the layer thickness and resulted in the preparation of a uniform oxide coating. (Fig. 4). Due to the homogeneity of MAO coatings, chemical analysis of the layers was performed using EDX at 50x magnification. The results of the determination show a different Zn representation in the MAO coating depending on the applied source frequency. In the case of using frequencies of 49 Hz (S1) and 95 Hz (S2), 0.6 wt% Zn (S1) and 0.8 wt% Zn (S2) were determined by EDX. On the surface of sample S3 prepared using a frequency of 222 Hz, the most significant Zn abundance was determined to be 1.1 wt%.

The 3D CPEM images of MAO coatings (Fig. 5a–d, g) were obtained by simultaneous AFM and SEM data acquisition. The correlation was performed by considering the offset so that the overlap corresponds to the AFM and SEM images. The SEM results of MAO coatings (Fig. 5b–e, h) highlight the topographic character of the MAO coatings and confirm the inhomogeneity of the layer. This is complemented by EDX mapping of the Zn distribution on the surface of the analysed MAO coatings (Fig. 5c–f, ch).

The presence of each phase of MAO coating was identified by XRD and the results in the form of XRD pattern are shown in Fig. 6. In the volumes of all the samples, the cubic Al phase (PDF Card No.: 03-065-2869) was determined as the most significant phase. A detailed XRD record of this majority phase is shown in Fig. 6b. Consistent with the composition of AlSi1MgMn, the hexagonal Al_9Mn_3Si phase (PDF Card No.: 01-089-4996) and the cubic phase $(MgO)_{0.3}(MnO)_{0.7}$ (PDF Card No.: 01-077-2381) were identified in the diffraction pattern (Fig. 6a). From the cross-section analysis by SEM (Fig. 4) and surface CPEM analysis including the mapping performed (Fig. 5), the presence of Zn in the MAO coating was confirmed. The diffraction record (Fig. 6a) confirms the presence of hexagonal zincite ZnO (PDF Card No.: 00-005-0664) in the MAO coating of samples S1, S2, S3. As a result of the discharge on the substrate surface, the Zn^{2+} ions contained in the electrolyte react with the EDTA-based additive to form a complex which, under the conditions of plasma discharge on the sample surface, decomposes to form an unstable hydroxide (Eq. (4)) with the subsequent evolution of ZnO (Eq. (5)), which thus becomes part of the MAO coating due to the intensity of the discharge.

Fig. 2. Morphological structure of sample surfaces. SEM images of (a) Sub, (b) Sp, (c) S1, (d) S2 and (e) S3.

Fig. 3. Determined roughness parameters of Sub, Sp, S1, S2, S3: (a) R_a ; (b) R_z ; (c) R_t ; (d) R_{Sm} .

Fig. 4. The thickness of MAO coating: a) S1; b) S2; c) S3.

The major phase of the MAO coating includes the established corundum phase $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (PDF Card No.: 00-046-1212), typical of aluminium alloys modified by the MAO process. The evolution of the stable oxide phase of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is described by the following equations and is dependent on the electrolyte concentration, discharge intensity, process conditions and cooling rate [28].

On the substrate surface, under MAO and alkaline electrolyte conditions, the aluminium partially dissolves and reacts to form an unstable

layer $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ (Eq. (6)(7)(8)). Plasma discharge and heat release from unstable hydroxide leads to the formation of $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Eq. (9)), which may also be accompanied by the formation of an amorphous phase in connection with the cooling rate. In accordance with the choice of discharge conditions and the released heat, a phase transformation occurred during the MAO process to form stable $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Eq. (10)) [29].

The MAO coating and substrate samples were analysed by XPS to identify the elements present in the near-surface region and their chemical states. Wide scan XPS spectra were added as separate figure to the Supplementary data, Fig. S1. To confirm the elemental composition of MAO coatings and substrate, broad spectra (not shown) and detail spectra in the near valence band region were measured (Fig. 7). The measurement results show the presence of major elements represented on the surface by Al, Zn, O and other impurities present such as Na, F and C. These findings correspond to the composition of the substrate described in 2.1. and 2.2. sections and in Table 2 as well as to the polishing, blasting and MAO treatments of the samples.

Based on the measured broad spectra, the individual strongest emission lines of the elements present (Al, Zn, O, C) were selected, and their detailed spectra were measured. These spectra were used to study the chemical state of each element on the sample surface. The photoemission spectra of each element were corrected for the charging effect. The photoelectron spectra of the Al 2p emission line are shown in Fig. 8, where two phases, metallic and oxidised, can be observed. In the sample

Fig. 5. Surface morphology and the presence of zinc on the MAO coating surface: (a), (d), (g) CPEM images of S1, S2, S3; (b), (e), (h) SEM images of S1, S2, S3; (c) (f) (ch) elemental mapping of zinc in MAO coating S1, S2, S3.

Fig. 6. The X-ray diffraction patterns of (a) MAO coatings (S1, S2, S3) and mechanically treated sample Sp, (b) detail of the majority phase.

surface modified by the MAO process, the Al is only in the oxidised form but differs in its intensity. It can be seen that the least of this phase is present in the sample S1. The Zn 2p spectrum is represented by a doublet at a binding energy of 1022.3 eV with a spin-orbit splitting of 23.1 eV (Fig. 8). Because of the slight difference between the metallic and oxidised states of zinc in the 2p spectrum, the chemical state of zinc was

determined by using of the modified Auger parameter, which is given by the sum of the binding energy of the 2p_{3/2} photoemission line and the kinetic energy of the Auger peak L3M45M45 [30]. Another advantage of this parameter is related to its independence of the sample charging. The Zn LMM Auger spectra of the samples are shown in (Fig. 8). After converting the spectrum to kinetic energy, the position of the Zn LMM Auger

Fig. 7. Detail XPS spectra of near valence band region of Sp, S1, S2 and S3 samples taken using Al anode of the X-ray source.

Fig. 8. Detail XPS analysis of different elements from Sp, S1, S2 and S3 samples.

peak at the kinetic energy scale was found at 986.7 eV, giving a value of the modified Auger parameter equal to 2009 eV. According to C. Wöll [31], this value corresponds to ZnO zinc oxide.

The spectra of oxygen O 1s (Fig. 8) are difficult to separate into individual components. The increased intensity of the spectra from the S1, S2 and S3 samples is probably due to zinc and aluminium oxides on the sample surface. The other components correspond to aluminium oxide (531 eV) and surface contamination (higher binding energy component). The strongest C 1s spectrum was observed in the case of Sp sample (see Fig. 8). Given the position of the peak at 285 eV, it is likely that hydrocarbons with C–C and C–H bonds are present due to surface contamination related to the application of surface blasting. The C 1s

spectra from the other samples were very weak, indicating the presence of C–C and C–H bonding, which may also be related to electrolyte decomposition products [32].

3.3. Surface wettability

From the determination of CA in distilled water and SBF solution (Fig. 9), it is evident that the application of surface treatments, especially blasting technology, led to the preparation of hydrophobic surfaces ($CA > 90^\circ$). Statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirms the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis ($p < 0.05$) that one of the CA means is statistically different. A statistically significant effect for the

Fig. 9. Wetting angles of samples Sub, Sp, S1, S2, S3: (a) distilled water and b) SBF solution.

preparation of surfaces S1, S2, and S3 with hydrophobic properties determined by distilled water (Fig. 9a) was confirmed for the blasting and MAO technology. MAO coatings containing ZnO and Al₂O₃ were not statistically significantly different ($p > 0.05$). CA determined in SBF solution (Fig. 9b) for Sub and Sp samples confirmed that CA was not statistically significantly different. Statistical agreement was also confirmed for CA in the case of MAO-coated samples S1, S2 and S3.

The effect of the technology used on the change in CA is evident in Fig. 10. In the case of the blasting method, there was a statistically significant change in the observed roughness parameters, demonstrating that the micro/nanostructure of the surface has a significant effect on its wettability [33,34]. The mechanically prepared irregular "leaf" surface structure represents a hydrophobic surface in the Sp sample, both in the case of measurements using distilled water (CA = $99.9^\circ \pm 6.9$) and SBF solution (CA = $99.8^\circ \pm 11.3$). A hierarchical surface prepared in this way can create open spaces where air can be trapped, leading to a higher CA [35].

The treated samples were then subjected to the MAO process with selected EDTA electrolytes to form hydrophobic layers with different Zn content. The increase in the hydrophobic properties is probably related to the presence of some organic molecules such as esters, carboxylic acids, etc., which may cause changes in the wettability of the surface [36]. The CA results indicate the influence of the composition of MAO coatings on the increase in hydrophobic properties. This is probably due to the presence of carbonate compounds in the MAO coating from the electrolyte. Depending on the procedure used for the preparation of MAO coatings, these may be EDTA degradation products, which can be represented by carboxylic acids or esters. It is also possible that the incorporation of Zn into the MAO coating occurred in the surroundings of the discharge with the direct participation of the Zn complex itself without subsequent decomposition reactions that can lead to oxidation

to CO₂ and NO_x [37,38].

3.4. Antibacterial activity of surfaces

The antibacterial activity was assessed based on the change in the number of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* colonies after 24 h of their incubation on Sub, Sp, S1, S2 and S3 samples (Fig. 11). The results show that after 24 h, reduction in the number of bacteria occurred in all the studied samples with the exception of the polished substrate. The reduction in activity was also observed in the Sp sample treated by blasting while achieving increased hydrophobic surface properties and roughness in all the parameters studied (R_a , R_z , R_t , R_{Sm}). The sample also showed hydrophobic surface properties due to increased roughness, which can effectively lead to bacterial adhesion elimination. Hydrophobic surfaces with micro/nano roughness eliminate contact sites suitable for cell adhesion due to the topography of the surfaces, which allows weak interactions for bacterial colonies through the tips of the modified surfaces [39]. The chemically different MAO surfaces S1, S2, and S3 containing ZnO and Al₂O₃ showed even more significant inhibition of bacterial growth than was the one observed in the Sp sample. The antibacterial activity of the ZnO-containing MAO surface can be associated with its partial solubility on Zn²⁺ ions and subsequent diffusion and interaction with the bacterial cell membrane. This results in irreversible damage to bacterial cells and, hence, enhanced antibacterial activity of the coating [40]. The most intensive antibacterial activity was determined in S3 sample, which had both the highest surface roughness (R_a , R_z , R_t) and the highest Zn content (1.1 wt%).

Fig. 10. Images from the wetting test of samples Sub, Sp, S1, S2, S3: a) distilled water and b) SBF solution.

Fig. 11. Antibacterial activity of surfaces: CFU/ml of *S.aureus* and *E.coli* after incubation on Sub, Sp, S1, S2, and S3 samples after 24 h.

3.5. Determination of stability of prepared coatings and corrosion behaviour

The stability of the MAO layer was evaluated at 1,7,14, and 28 days by immersion test in distilled water (pH 4.0) and SBF solution (pH 7.4). From the results in Fig. 12, it is clear that in distilled water, due to low pH, there is a dominant dissolution of ZnO of samples S1 and S2 after 1, 7 and 14 days. The dissolution mechanism of ZnO is to form Zn²⁺ and Zn(OH)⁺, as shown in Eqs. (11) and (12). As the pH increases to 7 and above in the SBF solution (Fig. 10), Zn(OH)₂ is formed, as shown in Eq. (13), which is partially soluble in water [41]. The amount of Zn released in the SBF solution is significantly less than that of the immersion test in distilled water. As with distilled water, the lowest Zn release occurs for sample S3. This fact indicates the structural stability of the MAO layer with the highest Zn content prepared under MAO conditions at the highest frequency (222 Hz). The hydrophobic properties of the MAO coating also contribute to the reduction of the released Zn due to the reduction of the contact area in the presence of an air barrier, which prevents the diffusion of solution ions. Thus, the structural stability of the MAO coating with hydrophobic properties allows the preparation of a stable Zn-containing coating [42].

The structural characterisation, antibacterial properties, and stability of the coatings were complemented by a description of the corrosion behaviour of ZnO-containing MAO coatings to define better the different corrosion properties of the samples used under 3.5 wt% NaCl solution conditions. There were different three areas tested on each sample to evaluate the results fluctuation and to minimize the possible variation of corrosion parameters. The results were evaluated for each potentiodynamic polarisation curve. Potentiodynamic measurements were performed on uncoated samples (Sub, Sp) and MAO coatings (S1, S2, S3)

using the Tafel extrapolation and the Stern-Geary method (Fig. 13), where corrosion parameters (Table 3), including corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (I_{corr}) and polarisation resistance (R_p) were evaluated [43]. The table also contains both Tafel parameters for anodic (β_a) and cathodic (β_c) area of the curve. The difference of corrosion parameters for each tested area was insignificant (variation coefficient <10 %), therefore only a typical polarisation curves and parameters determined from it were selected for publication. The individual typical polarisation curves for each sample were saved in the Supplementary data, Fig. S2. General corrosion was observed on the surface of the sample (S3) after polarisation measurements without the presence of pitting corrosion (Supplementary data, Fig. S3).

The results proved the improvement in corrosion resistance of MAO coatings and a simultaneous significant reduction in the corrosion current density I_{corr} values (Table 3). In a study by A. Bordbar-Khiabani et al. [44] the dependence of the effect of roughness on the corrosion

Fig. 13. Electrochemical corrosion behavior: potentiodynamic polarisation curves of mechanically treated aluminium alloys and MAO-coated samples.

Fig. 12. Determination of MAO coating stability in different environments: a) distilled water; b) SBF solution.

Table 3
Parameters of corrosion behaviour of samples.

Sample	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	β_a (mV/decade)	β_c (mV/decade)	R_p ($\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$)	C_R ($\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$)
Sub	-748.2	0.276	32.0	-280.9	99.35	2.86
Sp	-732.2	0.324	52.8	-123.8	54.33	3.37
S1	-940.9	0.053	91.4	-170.0	333.83	0.55
S2	-824.6	0.018	55.7	-57.8	638.75	0.19
S3	-920.4	0.070	83.4	-222.9	315.98	0.73

behaviour of aluminium alloys was not confirmed. When the MAO process was applied with different frequencies, a significant reduction of I_{corr} occurred; the micropores closed due to the penetration of electrolyte ions into the oxide layer and limited the penetration of Cl^- anions to the alloy substrate through the effluent channels. The nature of the morphology and pore closure is evident from the anodic response of the potentiodynamic curves (Fig. 13) exhibiting stable character with no significant fluctuations. The reduction in corrosion current density was mainly due to the formation of a thick layer of Al-based oxides and their barrier effect. Due to the dielectric nature of the layer, electric charge can only be transferred during the anodic reaction by the migration of ions from the solution through pores, crevices and other migration channels, which significantly reduces the corrosion reaction speed. The protective oxide layer locally dissolves once the critical potential is reached during the anodic polarisation, leading to exposure of the pristine surface underneath. This behaviour was evident the most in the case of the S2 sample, where breakdown potential characterised by the sudden change of curve is visible at approx. -150 mV vs. SCE. Size, volume, and nature of the internal defects used for charged ions migration are all determined by the parameters used during MAO, which also results in shifts of corrosion potential. The corrosion potential itself was not significantly affected by mechanical surface treatment but rather by the chemical composition of the surface and its microstructure and homogeneity [45].

4. Conclusions

In summary, a combination of methods, including the application of blasting and MAO technology, was used to prepare a modified surface with hydrophobic and antibacterial properties and enhanced corrosion resistance on the AlSi1MgMn substrate. The mechanical surface treatment provided significant surface roughening, which led to an increase in contact angle, directly related to the inhibition of the growth of the studied bacteria *S.aureus* and *E.coli* after 24 h. The prepared MAO coatings containing Zn indicated increased hydrophobic properties and antibacterial effects for both studied strains. The most significant antibacterial effect was determined for sample S3, which had the highest Zn content and was prepared at 222 Hz. Sample S3 showed the highest chemical stability after 1, 7, 14, and 28 days in distilled water and SBF solution. All MAO coatings, evaluated in a 3.5 % NaCl solution, showed increased corrosion resistance. In this study, results were obtained defining a procedure for the preparation of surfaces with increased roughness, accompanied by an increase in the contact angle and inhibition of the growth of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* bacteria after 24 h on the surface of the aluminium alloy. The use of the MAO technique allows the modification of aluminium alloy surfaces with the effective incorporation of ZnO into the MAO coating surface and the resulting antibacterial effect. For these reasons, antibacterial MAO coatings can be applied to surfaces with an increased risk of bacterial infection.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Roman Gabor: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Irena Šlamborová:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation,

Formal analysis. **Karel Mašek:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Marek Večer:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Grażyna Simha Martynková:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Josef Hlinka:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Michaela Tokarcíková:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Oldřich Motyka:** Methodology, Investigation. **Petr Běčák:** Visualization, Investigation. **Jana Seidlerová:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.06.193>.

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